

CYBER CRIME AND ITS PROTECTION

Dr. Manish Bhatnagar

*Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Jain Vishva Bharti Institute
(Deemed University), LADNUN, Rajasthan*

Dr. Pragati Bhatnagar

*Assistant Professor, Acharya Kalu Kanya Mahavidhyalaya, Jain Vishva Bharti Institute
(Deemed University), LADNUN, Rajasthan*

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Abstract

Present era is an era of digital technologies and artificial intelligence. AI and new digital technologies are bringing drastic changes in our life. We are performing our routine tasks through technology. We are using digital devices for routing financial transactions, for our academic and research purpose, for our business, for e-shopping, for booking our tickets etc. Although the use of technology has made our many tasks very easy and efficient but it has brought to us the danger of cyber frauds. Daily in news papers we are reading about the cyber frauds harming the very common man of our society. Not only the common man but also many reputed and educated persons often become the victim of cyber crime. Govt. has taken many initiatives and has established National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal but still there is lack of awareness regarding cybercrime and protection from cyber frauds. This paper discusses the problem of increasing cyber frauds, inculcating awareness in public to protect them from cyber fraud and initiatives taken by government to fight against the cyber crimes.

Key words – Cyber crime, Prevention Practices

Introduction

India is emerging itself into the world's leading digital hubs. While greater connectivity and a digital economy is giving large-scale progress, it also leave our growing societies open to new vulnerabilities. China is the world largest internet population of the world. We as the second largest internet population of the world just begun to develop a cyber security framework to protect these frauds. Meanwhile, cyber crimes know no borders and have evolved at a pace at par with emerging technologies.

Cyber fraud is continuously growing to a new age . It is not a new trend but massive increase in cyber fraud cases is alarming to open eye of every citizen of the nation. Teaching community is also the victim of such cases. According to government data massive surge in cybercrime incidents was reported in India with fraudsters cheating people of Rs 33,165 crore in the last four years, including Rs 22,812 crore in 2024, with several Tier 2 and 3 cities identified as cybercrime hotspots. Data compiled by the National Cyber Reporting Platform (NCRP), under the Ministry of Home Affairs, shows fraudsters cheated people of Rs 551 crore in 2021, Rs 2,306 crore in 2022, and Rs 7,496 in 2023. Stock trading scams accounted for the largest share, with losses of Rs 4,636 crore from 2,28,094 complaints. Investment-based scams caused losses of Rs 3,216 crore from 1,00,360 complaints, while Rs 1,616 crore was lost to “digital arrest” frauds across 63,481 complaints. It shows a that the problem is very big and we have to give an eye towards it.

“Domestic hotspots have been identified as Deoghar in Jharkhand, Deeg, Alwar, Jaipur, and Jodhpur in Rajasthan, Nuh in Haryana, Mathura and Gautam Buddha Nagar in Uttar Pradesh, Kolkata in WestBengal, Surat inGujarat, Nalanda and Nawada in Bihar, Bengaluru urban in Karnataka, and Kozhikode in Kerala.”

The steep rise in cybercrime cases, Union Home Minister Amit Shah is asked the Home Ministry to develop an e-FIR system, in which a citizen can file their complaint via NCRP. This will provide a hassle-free system to the cyber fraud victim, who lost Rs 10 lakh or above in cyber fraud. Multiple teams, including the Indian Cyber Crime Coordination Centre (I4C), are currently working on this aspect. It is proposed to make a nationalised cyber-police station of e-FIR in the NCRP portal where apart from lodging a complaint, e-FIR can also be filec. Later, the e-FIR will be transferred to their concerned jurisdiction police station for further investigation.

Last decade the number of cyber crimes reported across India continuously increased at a significant pace. Among the various crimes committed, cyber fraud has been a growing concern over the past few years, with financial losses valuing billions of Indian rupees annually. Every sectors such as Information Technology, healthcare, manufacturing, and finance, were most vulnerable to cyber crime. Additionally, small scale businesses were likely targets of cybercriminals. Among all Indian companies only 40% were in the progressive and above stages of cyber security readiness in 2024.

Cyber criminals are not only tracing private sector but also online, government agencies and systems like India’s unique citizen identification system - the Aadhaar number

, compromising extensive personal information . Bank details, address and biometrics of over a billion Indians was unknowingly taken up by unauthorized persons who can also misuse the same.

According to Indian express Data compiled by the Indian Cyber Crime Coordination Centre (I4C) shows nearly half of the 12 lakh cyber fraud complaints received in 2024 were perpetrated by fraudsters based in Southeast Asian countries — Cambodia, Myanmar, and Laos.

Some facts of cyber crime

One of the biggest factor in curbing cyber crime in India has been seen as the lack of awareness on cyber hygiene. Even when crimes were reported to authorities, the infrastructure and process to tackle such cases were largely inefficient. In 2018, the Ministry of Home Affairs of India set up the Indian Cyber Crime Coordination Centre (I4C) to serve as a framework to combat cyber crime. The government further launched the National Cybercrime Reporting Portal (NCRP) under the I4C in 2019 but due to lack of awareness people don't report on NCRP. In addition to this, the government has imposed a stringent content regulation policy on the internet and social media platforms. Cyber crime increased in because of increase in the expansion of the various investments in online mode. As the number of transactions in online mode is increasing the people engaged in cyber crimes are becoming more active and number of cyber crimes are increasing. Even artificial intelligence is becoming a friendly approach to cyber criminals and they are widely using various modes for threatening people and making money by tracking their financial transaction.

Best practices for Reducing the risk

Continuously development in generative artificial intelligence is leading to increase in cyber crimes. According to the World Economic Forum, the cost of cyber fraud could double between 2023 and 2027. Government agencies, private companies and individuals are all potential targets of identity theft, transactional fraud and ransomware. In the past five years, Phishing scams are the most common, but cyber investment scams are the most costly, with victims losing a huge amount every year. Scammers have also started to use generative AI tools in sophisticated fraud attempts, such as leveraging synthetic audio and video to create deep fakes, programming of large language models to create phishing and business e-mail compromise campaigns and utilizing social media platforms to execute various impersonation schemes.

We can adopt some practices which will significantly increase the security surrounding towards the data, assets and overall online safety.

Continually Update our Computer and Mobile Devices

Cybercriminals frequently gain access to information by using known flaws in the software and operating systems that run in our computers or phones. The best defense is to keep software, web browsers, and operating systems up to date so as to protect our digital devices. Regularly updating the computer and mobile devices is crucial as it ensures that any known security flaws are patched, reducing the risk of exploitation by malicious actors. It prevents us from being a victim of a cyber attack.

Employ Antivirus Software and Anti-malware Protection on Computers

Cybercriminals also use technical attacks to deploy viruses, botnets, malware, keyloggers and spyware to infect or take control of our computer. There are many free antivirus software which we can use and purchase once when the free the trial is over. Additionally, there are hundreds of antivirus applications available in the market, we can choose from that. We must ensure to select software solutions that provide us adequate protection, keep our system and software updated with the latest virus definitions, and schedule regular full scans, preferably at least once per week.

Password strength should be strong

For each account, we must use the strong password and update it regularly. We can create strong passwords by combining uppercase and lowercase letters, unique characters and numbers. We should avoid including personal information in our passwords and take care of not using the same password for multiple accounts. We must never write down passwords on paper or share them with anyone. For mobile devices, we can set up a PIN (or passcode) or facial recognition setting and activate the auto-lock feature in device settings. Her enabling of multi-factor authentication (MFA) will add an extra layer of protection for our information.

Strengthen Network at Home

Malicious cyber actors may attack on our home network to gain access to personal, private and confidential information. To protect against these threats, start by setting a strong password for our Wi-Fi network and select the appropriate encryption, beginning with at least Wi-Fi Protected Access 2 (WPA2). We must regularly update our router's software. It is also advisable to hide our network, keeping it concealed from unauthorized connections. We can

also purchase protection against cyberattacks for every internet-connected device at our home, including game consoles, smart TVs and other appliances.

Protection from cyber attacks

Cyber attacks may be in form of phishing or vishing. Phishing is when cyber criminals use deceptive emails or messages to trap our personal or financial information, while vishing involves fraudulent phone calls with the goal to collect the information. The best defense for us is staying vigilant. If we receive a request for personal or financial information from an unknown source, take a moment to think and try to verify their legitimacy. We can Contact with the concerned organization or individual directly to confirm the request's authenticity. We must be cautious about clicking on links, opening attachments or sharing sensitive details.

Having a Back Up of Data

Every electronic gadget or device may become compromised or crash. Backing up the data on our devices will help us in recovering our information in these situations. We can back up our information by regularly copying your files to an external hard drive, using cloud storage services or employing specialized backup software. These practices ensure that our data remains secure, easily recoverable, and protected against unexpected mishaps or device failures.

Aware Children and Family About Internet Security

Young children are vulnerable to even the most basic of cyber tricks. Teenagers, while tech savvy, are online more frequently and often visit riskier sites, such as file sharing platforms for movies, videos and games. Older persons possessing financial assets have limited digital knowledge easily become victim of cyber crimes. They should be educated for cyber awareness. We must have an environment of open dialogue to educate our children about safe online practices, including the importance of strong passwords, recognizing malicious email attempts, and avoiding sharing personal information with strangers.

Protect Against theft of personal information

Our personal information can be used to commit fraud, such as account takeovers, unauthorized money transfers or new lines of credit opened in our name. This may result from malware on our computer, social engineering that tricks for taking our emotional control and providing the information which will help a thief for stealing our mail or trash to access personally identifiable information. We can protect identity theft by shredding sensitive documents, avoiding interaction with suspicious links and attachments in our email, learning

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to recognize and block fishing attacks. We should also continuously review our credit report on a regular basis.

What a victim should do

If a person becomes a victim of cyber fraud or cyber attack he must report on 1930 help line number. We must not share our personal information online to unknown persons. We must never give our account numbers, credit or debit card information, pin number or any other highly sensitive information just because someone is asking politely or threatening us. Cyber criminals may black mail us and may demand for money transfer. We may report to nearby police station for such threatening. We must ensure that any detail to be submitted only to trusted people. When in doubt, we must verify the request first before taking any action. By taking regular precautions and staying connected with the good habits we can live a safe life and prevent ourself from becoming victims of cyber fraud or crime. The main purpose of cyber fraud awareness is to educate and guide individuals on safeguarding themselves from harmful cyber activities. For cyber awareness various campaign has been launched by UGC in every university and colleges so that every stake holder must be updated and take action for the protection of cyber fraud.

Conclusion-

Use of digital technologies and AI has no doubt made our life very easy and efficient. We are able to perform many of our routine tasks such as filling our electricity bill, our wards school/college fee, purchasing routine grocery items, bank transactions at a mouse click. Although this is a revolutionary change for mankind but it has brought the danger of cyber fraud for every common man. We all are in danger and daily we hear the news of cyber fraud even with most educated and reputed people of society. If we want to protect ourself there is need to follow cyber hygiene. Govt. has taken many initiatives like reporting the crime immediately on toll free number 1930 and on NCRP. Due to lack of awareness we don't follow the advices given to us while using digital devices and we become the victim of cyber fraud. It is now high time to be very vigilant while using digital technology following the cyber security initiatives and advices so that we may remain protected against any such cyber frauds

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